

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF A “HEALTHY FUTURE GENERATION”

Qudratullaev Jaloliddin Ibrahimovich

TerDU Faculty of Social Sciences

A student of the field of applied psychology

Abstract: in this article, the stages of the effective activities carried out in order to increase the importance of physical education and sports games, to improve the morale of the young generation, to improve their mental abilities, and to increase their importance are highlighted in a technological manner.

Key words: education, education, sport, physical education, spiritual education, school, health improvement.

РОЛЬ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ «ЗДОРОВОГО БУДУЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ»

Кудратуллаев Джалолиддин Ибрагимович

ТерГУ Факультет социальных наук

студент прикладной психологии

Аннотация: в данной статье выделены этапы эффективной деятельности, проводимой в целях повышения значимости занятий физкультурой и спортивными играми, повышения морального духа подрастающего поколения, совершенствования их умственных способностей, повышения их значимости в технологический способ.

Ключевые слова: воспитание, воспитание, спорт, физическое воспитание, духовное воспитание, школа, оздоровление.

“SOG‘LOM KELAJAK AVLOD”NI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA JISMONIY TARBIYANING O‘RNI

Qudratullayev Jaloliddin Ibrohimovich

TerDU Ijtimoiy fanlar fakulteti

amaliy psixologiya ta'lim yo'nalishi talabasi

Annotatsiya: uchbu maqolada, yosh avlodni ma'naviy yuksaltirish, aqliy qobiliyatini shakllantirishda sog'lomlashtirish, jismoniy tarbiya va sport o'yinlarining o'rni, ahamiyatini oshirish borasida olib borilayotgan samarali faoliyatlarning bosqichlari texnologik tartibda yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim, tarbiya, sport, jismoniy tarbiya, ma'naviy tarbiya, maktab, sog'lomlashtirish.

Prospect this upcoming life, future means. In our people, " Expect he said, " Let it shine, let it shine " there is a saying. This saying more to the children relatively is used. That is, our people to young people goodness please come happy let it be saying intention they do Of course each one parents own to his child happy the future wishes. This is the dream our hooray in our country state scale may have risen. Our government young people the future for very big things done is increasing. In our country children perfection for everyone how much mood Young generation physical healthy, spiritual perfect by doing education of this day current of duties is considered

Education education the main direction of the process as being looked at this task solution reach a lot in terms of physical education right to the road to be placed and abilities in formation different in topics our people in the field of sports in the inheritance is available has been children from the games appropriate use important importance occupation is enough.

Independent to the field of sports in Uzbekistan separately attention is being directed. Children and teenagers physical in terms of perfect by doing bring up state of the program main to the content is spinning. Because the future generations destiny today's healthy of our people spiritual and physical perfection with depends. This about in our country young generation physical and spiritual health strengthening of our children healthy marriage style provide, in them sportsman love feelings strengthen on the surface wide scope affairs done is increasing.

It is known that our people the most respectable and responsible from training one is education. To independence when achieved, in young people mind and national thinking formation, spirituality and enlightenment high to the degree to raise separately attention be given started Because it is important task only spiritual - moral education through solution to be done can Man spirituality and Enlightenment, intelligence, high morals, good manners talent, potential, virtue, courage and so on education is a product.

Children of sports development the future of young people physically, mentally healthy of education is a guarantee. This while of our children in the future each how modern to technologies based on knowledge in mastering to resistances not meet provides . Because we humanity in history unforgettable turning circuit Science, technology and technology progress in the 21st century we are living, moreover, in our country legal democratic state and citizenship society set up reach process is passing The world community with different in directions cooperation to do in front of us standing economic and social political issues solution reach and our society spiritual and educational in terms of improvement through our people prosperity to provide, our citizens, family and generation each bilaterally perfect (also physically, too spiritual in terms of healthy), wise, progressive thoughtful and intelligent to be we are striving In

this place young people and teenagers between healthy marriage style in creating physical education and sports height to emphasize it is permissible.

A lot yearly to history have has been Turan on the ground living coming our ancestors our ancestors too centuries during physical educational sports games with engaged in came This we people oral " Alpomish ", " Goro'gli ", from " Avazbek " epics we know Therefore our ancestors too physically energetically, spiritually healthy children have grown and of them people heroes of myth and legends matured came out Today's in the day too our youth so mature person ie perfect a person in education physical education and of sports place in particular research take is going Education in the system, before school education in institutions, middle special in their schools this about efficient activities take is going

Today is the day of experts scientific studies as a result theoretical and organizational knowledge and practice appropriation the following steps technological in order done increase explanation is being done.

1. Har one of a person own health in strengthening personally himself in charge that physical culture education through realize to get provide.

2. Current in time ecological disorders, external of the environment pollution, natural and technological of accidents growth, man physical of health to the front new requirements is putting about to knowledge have that is happening provide.

3. Physical education and sports in the country development, man health more to strengthen directed state leadership by acceptance being done law, decree, decisions own in time informed to be, to them being placed requirements in the country residence doing each one citizen himself for set given belongs to instructions to perform provide that it is his duty to know

4. It is known that every one a person always needs three types of nutrition. This material, spiritual and physical are nutrition. Of these physical of nutrition each one to himself necessary level his own diary vital from experience come out done increase provider to knowledge have to be.

5. Har one a person his own physical opportunities knowledge, his sports training and competitions conditions high the result demonstration to prepare about scientific-theoretical-practical to knowledge have to be

6. Har a person is his lifestyle conditions which physical movement from his actions how when using himself physical development and preparation where level effect to give about knowledge and to experiences have to be

7. Har a man himself living in the area region, country, continent, world scale physical education and about sports all belongs to from the data informed being

standing physical culture education technology above in order done increase, of people physical culture in formation main of the factors one being service does.

In short, it is the duty of all citizens to create a foundation for their spiritual and material development through the physical health of the future generation. We will achieve our goal only when physical training and sports of our youth become an integral part of our daily life.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaevna H. F., Menglimamat P. J. THE IMPORTANCE OF FORMING A READING CULTURE IN THE PROCESS OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.

2. Abdullaevna H. F., Menglimamat P. J. THE IMPORTANCE OF EXTRACURRICULAR WORK IN THE CULTIVATION OF CREATIVE ABILITIES OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS //European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol. – 2019. – Т. 7. – №. 12.

3. Khaitova, F.A. 2023. «CREATIVE APPROACH TO FORMING A CULTURE OF LEARNING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION». *Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences* 2 (5):123-27.

<http://www.econferences.ru/index.php/tafps/article/view/4504>.

4. Abdullaevna H. F., Doniyorovna R. M. Requirements for the formation of reading culture //Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR). – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 5. – С. 240-245.

5. Хаитова, Ф.А. (2023). ТВОРЧЕСКИЙ ПОДХОД К ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ КУЛЬТУРЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В НАЧАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. *Теоретические аспекты становления педагогической науки*, 2 (5), 123-127.

6. Хайитова, Ф. А. (2021). Технологии креативного подхода к развитию речи младших школьников. In *Инновации в науке, обществе, образовании* (pp. 130-149).

7. Khaitova, F. A. (2023). CREATIVE APPROACH TO FORMING A CULTURE OF LEARNING IN PRIMARY EDUCATION. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(5), 123-127.